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First PSD data from NEG coating

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ABSTRACT

This is I.FAST Deliverable Report D10.4 – First PSD (Photon Stimulated Desorption) data from NEG coating.

The Report summarises main achievement of Task 10.5 and includes the following:

- design and manufacturing of samples used withing the task,
- developing and implying the sample cleaning procedure,
- coating the samples with NEG films and testing their pumping properties,
- and, finally, first PSD results obtained on SR beamlines at DLS and SOLEIL

I.FAST Consortium, 2024

For more information on IFAST, its partners and contributors please see <https://ifast-project.eu/>

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TABLE OF CONTENTS

1	INTRODUCTION.....	4
2	SAMPLE PREPARATION.....	5
2.1	THREE-GAUGE METHOD	5
2.2	SAMPLE DESIGN AND MANUFACTURING	6
2.2.1	<i>Prototype 0</i>	6
2.2.2	<i>IFAST samples 1 and 3</i>	8
2.3	DEVELOPMENT OF CLEANING PROCEDURE AT DESY	11
2.4	NEG FILM DEPOSITION AND PUMPING TEST AT UKRI.....	12
2.4.1	<i>Deposition at Daresbury Laboratory</i>	12
2.4.2	<i>NEG FILM PUMPING TEST</i>	13
3	PSD MEASUREMENTS AT DLS AND SOLEIL	15
3.1	TEST AT DLS	15
3.1.1	<i>Introduction</i>	15
3.1.2	<i>PSD beamline FE10B</i>	16
3.1.3	<i>Data collection and analysis</i>	18
3.1.4	<i>Preliminary results and conclusions</i>	19
3.2	TEST AT SYNCHROTRON SOLEIL	22
3.2.1	<i>Introduction</i>	22
3.2.2	<i>PSD beamline D08-1</i>	23
3.2.3	<i>Data collection and analysis</i>	24
3.2.4	<i>Preliminary Results and Conclusions</i>	25
4	FUTURE PLANS / CONCLUSION / RELATION TO OTHER IFAST WORK	28
5	REFERENCES.....	29

Executive summary.

This is I.FAST Deliverable Report D10.4 – First PSD data from NEG coating. The Report summarizes main achievement of Task 10.5 and includes the following: Design and manufacturing of samples used within the task, developing and employing the sample cleaning procedure, NEG coating and pumping properties and, finally, first PSD results obtained at DLS and SOLEIL.

1 Introduction

The accelerator vacuum chamber must provide specified vacuum condition for the charged particle beam(s). The non-evaporable getter (NEG) coating is a solution that originally invented in CERN in 1990s to provide a distributed pumping speed along the vacuum chamber [1-5]. This solution is already employed in many particle accelerators in the world: LHC and LEIR at CERN, ESRF and SOLEIL in France, DLS in UK, MAX-IV in Sweden, ELETTRA in Italy, RHIC in USA, etc. [6-19]. IFAST Task 10.5 aims to produce and systematically test the prototypes of accelerator vacuum chamber coated with various non-evaporable getter (NEG) coatings and measure their figure of merit, Photon Stimulated Desorption (PSD), in conditions close to operation in particle accelerators, i.e. under synchrotron radiation (SR) on SR beamlines.

Two dedicated synchrotron radiation (SR) beamlines were employed: newly built at Diamond Light Source (DLS) and reconditioned SOLEIL synchrotron. Facilities for photon stimulated desorption (PSD) yield measurement were built on these beamlines employing an STFC experience in experimental studies of PSD/ESD from sorbing surfaces.

For the experimental programme, DLS and SOLEIL provided the vacuum chamber prototypes, which have been cleaned at DESY and coated with NEG film at STFC. Several types of NEG coating will be explored, with varying parameters such as composition, morphology and thickness of the NEG coating.

The vacuum chamber prototypes will be installed on dedicated SR beamlines at DLS and SOLEIL then irradiated following an agreed procedure: after NEG activation to different temperatures, after a few cycles of exposing to air and re-activation, and SR induced re-activation (without heating). The obtained results are jointly analysed by STFC, DLS, SOLEIL and DESY vacuum experts and will be published in scientific journals.

2 Sample preparation

2.1 THREE-GAUGE METHOD

To accurately predict a behaviour of average gas density (or pressure) along the beam vacuum chamber coated with NEG, the gas dynamics model required PSD yields as a function of photon accumulated dose, $\eta(D)$, and sticking probabilities, α , for sorbing gases.

Fig. 1: Schematic layout of vacuum chamber under SR.

The average gas density along the beam chamber with a length L for non-sorbing gases (i.e. for $\alpha = 0$) irradiated by SR is:

$$\langle n_L \rangle = q \left(\frac{L^2}{12u} + \frac{L}{2S_p} \right)$$

$$\langle n_L \rangle \approx \eta \Gamma \frac{L^2}{12u} = \eta \Gamma \frac{L^2}{3\bar{v}\pi d^2}$$

And for sorbing gases (i.e. for $\alpha > 0$), it is:

$$\langle n_L \rangle = \frac{q}{c} \left(1 - \frac{\tanh\left(\sqrt{\frac{c}{u}} \frac{L}{2}\right)}{\sqrt{\frac{c}{u}} \frac{L}{2} \left(1 + \frac{\sqrt{cu}}{S_p} \tanh\left(\sqrt{\frac{c}{u}} \frac{L}{2}\right) \right)} \right)$$

$$\langle n_L \rangle \approx \frac{\eta \Gamma}{c} = \frac{\eta \Gamma}{\alpha} \frac{4}{\pi d}$$

A commonly used vacuum conductance method for measuring PSD yields is perfectly suitable for non-sorbing vacuum chambers. However, it is not suitable for accurate measurements of $\eta(D)$ and α for NEG coated vacuum chambers [5,20]. In this case, a so-called three-gauge method is perfectly suitable. In this method one gauge is placed in the middle of the tube at $z = 0$ and two others at either end of tube. Thus, the middle gauge measure pressure in the middle of the chamber in a condition close to one in accelerator. The ratio $\eta(D)/\alpha$ is calculated directly from the middle gauge pressure measurements, and then this ratio can be directly used for modelling vacuum in future accelerators. The only complication of this method is that it required three gauges instead of two, and specially designed sample with a vacuum port for a middle gauge.

2.2 SAMPLE DESIGN AND MANUFACTURING

2.2.1 Prototype 0

2.2.1.1 Prototype 0 design

The first test vessels installed on FE10B were designed internally at Diamond, before being manufactured by Kurt J. Lesker Company Ltd. While they are not directly representative of the Diamond or Diamond-II storage rings, the straightforward geometry aids interpretation of the PSD yields. The DN40 vessel is also well suited to NEG coating and on this basis was chosen for the initial PSD measurements on FE10B.

The vessels were manufactured from 304L stainless-steel with DN40 flanges, they have an internal diameter of 34.9 mm and a length of 1000 mm, see fig. 2 (a). The main body of the vessel is circular in profile and welded either side are 880 mm long water-cooling channels. Having two cooling channels allows for the test vessel to be orientated either inboard or outboard relative to the beam.

To perform three-gauge measurements, a necessary feature of the test vessels is the central port, shown in further detail in fig. 2(b). The port features a 10 mm diameter hole to the main body of the vessel and has an internal diameter of 26 mm. These dimensions were chosen to make welding the central port simpler and provide sufficient space for the conditioning assembly and central RGA.

The most recent measurements performed using FE10B are based on test vessels designed and manufactured specifically for the I.FAST project. This design work was led by SOLEIL and the vessel supplied to Diamond is shown in fig. 3.

Fig. 2: Prototype 0: Diamond designed stainless-steel DN40 vessel (34.9 mm ID) at 1000 mm in length. (a) is a top-down view of the vessel and (b) the internal profile of the central DN40 port.

2.2.1.2 Central port design

As mentioned above, a requirement for the three-gauge method is the central port for a third RGA. As this central port cannot be NEG-coated, care must be taken to reduce or eliminate the effects of secondary electrons or scattered photons on the vessel walls in this space. To this end, conditioning assemblies have been designed and built at Diamond to block both scattered photons and electrons, as well as pre-condition the vessel walls via electron bombardment. This takes advantage of the ‘memory effect’ of desorption and reduces the overall outgassing.

Shown in fig. 3 are the two types of central port conditioning assembly installed and used on FE10B. Figure 3(a) shows the ‘cone’ type assembly used for the stainless-steel DN40 vessels. The cone is supported by a central stainless-steel leg, providing the bias voltage, and two legs either side are used to support a tungsten filament. This filament is located inside the cone body and is the electron source for bombardment. The cone and filament are mounted inside a DN40 tee piece with a DN16 side port for an electrical feedthrough which provides the cone bias voltage and filament power. Figure 3(b) shows a modified assembly used for the DN20 OFS-Cu vessels. The cone has been replaced with a flat machined plate, and this is located inside the DN16 body of the central port.

The operating principle for both assemblies is identical, a current of between 1.8 and 1.9 A is supplied to the tungsten filament while a bias voltage of between 60 and 300 V can be applied to the cone/plate. Through a change in bias voltage polarity, it is possible to condition both the cone/plate or the surrounding vessel walls. This results in between 5 and 10 mA of drain current which is sufficient to condition the cone over a 24-hour period. This approach to the design has taken some time due to the space and machining requirements but has proven to be flexible and adaptable to the two types of vessels used.

Fig. 3: Collection a) shows the ‘cone’-type degassing assembly used for the stainless-steel - vessels while b) shows the plate-type assembly used for the I.FAST OFS-Cu vessels.

2.2.2 IFAST samples 1 and 3

2.2.2.1 Sample design

The design of the PSD Sample Vacuum Chambers for IFAST was derived from an existing design of copper-body vacuum vessels already used on SOLEIL's PSD experiment as foreseen for future machine upgrade. In the trend of other accelerators, OFS pipes (CuAg) with CuCr1Zr CF40 connecting flanges were used to down-scale vacuum vessel aperture to 20 mm diameter or lower, keeping a good impedance at low apertures. The design was also inspired from Diamond Light Source (DLS) vessels to adapt a central mini-port also made of CuCr1Zr (CF16) for 3-gauge measurement, allowing the possibility to add an extra point of vacuum measurement in the centre of the tube (see fig. 4). The main body is water-cooled as it will be impinged by photons during the experiments in order to reduce the thermal contribution. A simple copper tube was attached to the OFS vacuum pipe bound mechanically and sealed with a thermal conductive paste. These PSD samples will be NEG-coated with coatings of different natures for their studies.

Fig. 4: 3D CAD Design of the PSD Sample Vacuum Chamber with Central Mini-port.

A great care was taken in the conception of the central mini-port as it will not be NEG-coated, thus being a source of higher outgassing, that could interfere with the desorption measurements. The aperture was reduced, and the geometry adapted (see fig. 5). Nevertheless, it will be necessary to precondition the central port in order to reduce its photodesorption yield if secondary photons interact inside on its non-coated surfaces (see fig. 6). Therefore, an assembly with a filament was designed and installed in front of the measuring port to condition these non-NEG-coated surfaces with low-energy electrons prior to the experiment. At SOLEIL's a standard RGA manufacturer's filament was used and placed in front of the mini-port with the possibility to polarize the filament plate up to a positive 600 Volt voltage in order to condition the port, and to a negative -600 Volts voltage to condition the filaments plate itself. The design was easy, cheap and robust (see fig.7).

Fig. 5: The Central CuCr1Zr CF16 Mini-port.

Fig. 6 : Vertical Cut on the Centre Mini-port (CF16).

Fig. 7: SOLEIL's Filament as seen from the CF16 Mini-port, back view polarization, and holder.

2.2.2.2 Manufacturing

The execution drawings and the manufacturing of the PSD samples were contracted to a well-established vacuum chamber manufacturer (SAES RIAL Vacuum), meant to be produced within 16 weeks. They were ordered beginning 2022 and scheduled for mid-2022, but they were delivered beginning October 2022. Straightness tolerances were a little bit difficult to obtain, but the vessels

were well made and vacuum performance rights (see figs. 8 and 9

Fig & Fig. 9).

Fig. 8: Picture of a PSD Vacuum Chambers Freshly Manufactured.

The main body was a pipe made of OFS Copper (Cu 10700 with 0.1% Ag) with a very good electrical conductivity compatible with impedance of future machine upgrade. The connecting CF40 flanges and the mini-port with a CF16 flange were made of CuCr1Zr (CW106C). It was asked to have the hardness of 150 HB, if possible (120 HB minimum), and high tensile strength of 450 N/mm², if possible (400 N/mm² minimum). This allows to manufacture CF flanges in copper-based material and to use only Titanium electrode / inert gas welding (TiG) for assembling parts. Three stainless-steel feet-stands and two reference supports for metrology (Ø 8 mm) were added. The chambers were also provided with aluminium stiffener plates for handling, though copper-based vacuum chambers are softer than the traditional stainless-steel ones (see figs. 8). A cooling channel was attached to the chambers as it was foreseen to sustain a power-load from the photons beam whom it should be exposed to. For water cooling, a simple copper pipe, equipped with union Swagelok® connectors, was mechanically attached to the main vacuum pipe at the feet positions, and a thermal paste was used for a good heat transfer. The choice and application of the thermal paste happened to be not that simple, and an aluminium-filled thermally conductive epoxy that is NEG activation temperatures compatible was finally chosen (DURALCO® 132 from COTRONICS®).

Fig. 9: A CuCr1Zr CF40 Connecting Flange.

2.2.2.3 The Central Measuring Port

The main point of interest from the foreseen experiment is to be able to measure the vacuum in the middle of the tested vacuum chamber as it is required to fully characterize to vacuum profile along

the chamber whether it presents pure outgassing or shows pumping properties with an activated NEG-coating. As mentioned, a great care should be taken concerning the outgassing of the extra point of measure. However, with the initial schedule of a preliminary experiment to test the setup, planned for end-2022, a simple design was chosen with existing available parts. An assembly was constructed with standard CF40 components in order to fit a residual gas analyzer, an already in-tunnel wired cold cathode gauge and the new degassing filament assembly (see fig. 10). AT SOLEIL's the vacuum measurement device was not optimized for lowering outgassing but imply to be ready for a first preliminary experiment that would be conducted during the work-study internship of a student, Jonathan Gaudio, from 2022 to 2023 school period. By lakes of resources, the design was kept as is for the first IFAST experiment.

Fig. 10: The SOLEIL's Central Measuring Assembly with RGA, Outgazing Filament and Penning Gauge.

2.3 DEVELOPMENT OF CLEANING PROCEDURE AT DESY

A sample preparation procedure was created at DESY to clean samples for NEG coating for pumping property measurements. The preparation procedure was designed for cleaning OFS-Cu CW019A (CuAg0.10(OF)) chamber material. The cleaning procedure was as follows:

Degreasing

- ElmaClean (1.5%) in Ultrasonic bath at 65 °C for 15 minutes
- Rinse with demineralised water (DMW) until conductivity < 0.1 $\mu\text{S}/\text{m}$
- Rinse with Isopropanol
- N₂ drying for 5 minutes
- Sample places in air dryer at 60 °C for 2 hours

Etching

- Rinse with DMW until conductivity < 0.4 $\mu\text{S}/\text{m}$
- Rinse with Ammonium Persulfate ((NH₄)₂S₂O₈) (100g/l) + ammonium citrate (NH₄CH₃CO₂) (1g/l) at room temperature for 5 minutes
- DMW Rinse, N₂ drying and DMW Rinse, each 2 minutes

- Rinse with Ammonium Acetate ($C_6H_{17}N_3O_7$) (50g/l) at room temperature for 5 minutes
- DMW Rinse, N_2 drying and DMW Rinse, each 2 minutes
- N_2 drying for 5 minutes
- Rinse with Isopropanol for 1 minute
- N_2 drying for 10 minutes

The tubes are then stored in N_2 until ready to be deposited or sent to another facility

2.4 NEG FILM DEPOSITION AND PUMPING TEST AT UKRI

2.4.1 Deposition at Daresbury Laboratory.

Samples were created at Daresbury Laboratory using the DC cylindrical magnetron deposition facility illustrated in fig 11. An external Solenoid magnet, 1 m in length with a 220 mm inner bore, is used to coat the 1 m long samples. High purity Krypton gas was injected into the system for use as sputtering gas. The system was baked for 24 hours at 200 °C before deposition began, with a base pressure of $4-6 \times 10^{-10}$ mbar was achieved.

Two types of targets were used, a TiZrV alloy target was used for an initial prototype sample, while a twisted wire target, comprised of 1-mm wires of Ti, Zr and V was used for IFAST Samples 1 and 3.

For each deposition, witness samples made of copper foil were placed at each end of the sample tube. These samples were used for coating characterisation.

Table 1: NEG coating deposition parameters.

Parameter	Unit	Sample 0	Sample 1	Sample 3
Target		TiZrV alloy	3 x 1 mm TiZrV twisted wire	3 x 1 mm TiZrV twisted wire
Power (Pulsed)	W	75	76 - 85	75-78
Current	A	0.54	0.47 – 0.51	0.43 – 0.46
Voltage	V	139	161 – 167	167 – 181

Solenoid Current	A	23.8	16 - 18	15.7 – 18.0
Solenoid Voltage	V	81	60	63-64
Pressure	mbar	6×10^{-2}	2.5×10^{-2}	2.8×10^{-2}
Duration	HH:mm	02:00	05:16	05:08

2.4.2 NEG FILM PUMPING TEST

The samples were installed in the pumping property evaluation facility at UKRI/STFC Daresbury Laboratory, schematically shown in fig 12.

Fig. 12: Schematic of pumping property evaluation facility at UKRI/STFC Daresbury Laboratory.

They were subject to ASTeC standard bakeout and activation cycle [5], shown in fig. 13. The activation temperature was 160 °C for Prototype 0 and 180 °C for Samples 1 and 3. Prototype 0 was also subject to some ESD testing, but due to a failure of an RGA during measurements, readings could not be taken. Gas injection was performed with H₂, CO for prototype 0, with the addition of CO₂ for the tests with sample 1 and 3.

Fig. 23: Schematic of pumping property evaluation facility at UKRI/STFC Daresbury Laboratory.

The pumping property evaluation facility were modelled in MOLFLOW to run test-particle Monte-Carlo (TPMC) simulations for different types of the sample to allow extraction of sticking probability from the pressure ratios obtained in gas injection. The results are shown in fig. 14.

Fig. 34: The results of TPMC modelling for Prototype 0 and Samples 1 and 3.

The pumping results are shown in Table 2. The Ratio obtained

Table 2: NEG coating deposition parameters.

	Prototype 0		Sample 1		Sample 3	
	Ratio	Sticking probability	Ratio	Sticking probability	Ratio	Sticking probability
H ₂	1.8	6×10 ⁻⁴	450	0.005	14	0.001
CO	97	0.013	700	0.01	331	0.008
CO ₂	-	-	2000	0.03	890	0.01

3 PSD measurements at DLS and SOLEIL

3.1 TEST AT DLS

3.1.1 Introduction

In support of the Diamond-II upgrade programme, three new vacuum systems for the study of NEG-coated vessels have been designed and built at the Diamond Light Source. The complementary facilities allow for the NEG coating of vacuum vessels, measurement of their pumping performance, and to investigate the gas desorption from incident synchrotron radiation.

This last facility is a photon-stimulated desorption (PSD) front-end known as ‘FE10B’ and is located wholly within the storage ring vault. It is intended for the irradiation of vessels and assemblies similar to the existing Diamond storage ring as well as the upcoming Diamond-II storage ring.

The front-end was installed between 2020 and 2021 in two phases, first was the upstream ‘front-end’ section which was followed by the experimental end-station. The development of this front-end was well aligned with the timescales of the I.FAST Project’s Work Package 10.5. As such, Diamond has been able to study test vessels developed both in-house and with SOLEIL, and then coated by partners at UKRI.

Fig. 15: Pictures showing (a) the upstream section of FE10B, and (b) side view of the experimental end-station with a DN40 stainless-steel vessel installed.

Shown in fig. 15 are photographs of FE10B covering (a) the upstream portion and (b) the end-station.

3.1.2 PSD beamline FE10B

The Diamond storage ring typically operates with a stored current of $I = 300$ mA at an energy of $E = 3$ GeV. The PSD front-end ‘FE10B’ is located on a bending magnet source and at these machine parameters the photon flux is $\Gamma = 2.36 \times 10^{17}$ photons/s at a critical energy of $\varepsilon_c = 8.379$ keV (for a DN40 test vessel).

As mentioned above, the front-end is split into two sections: a typical Diamond dipole front-end and an experimental end-station. The layout for the upstream ‘front-end’ section is shown in fig. 16.

Fig. 16: Side-view drawing of FE10B vacuum arrangement, key features of the front-end are highlighted.

Moving from upstream to downstream (right-to-left in Fig. 16) multiple modules, the use of modules is to simplify installation. First is a beam-defining aperture and pneumatically controlled photon absorber (ABSB-01). The aperture and absorber are then isolated downstream by a vacuum gate valve

(VALVE-01) and fast-acting valve which protect against the accidental release of gas from the end station into the storage ring. A transport pipe with central pumping station leads to a set of beam-defining horizontal slits (SLITS). These define the width of the beam, with the slit separation ranging between 0 and 17.55 mm, giving a beamwidth at the test vessel of up to 23 mm.

The final two modules are a conductance limiting orifice (ORIFICE) consisting of a conically tapered copper body (28 to 30 mm diameter, N₂ equivalent conductance of 54.2 l/s) and a gate valve (VALVE-02) which isolates the end-station.

The pressures in both the front-end and end-station are monitored with cold cathode gauges (of the inverted magnetron type) and the vessels are pumped by differential diode-type ion pumps with pumping speeds between 150 and 500 l/s, leading to base pressures of around 2×10^{-10} mbar.

The experimental end-station then begins following VALVE-02 and is shown in fig. 17.

Fig. 17: Side-view drawing of the FE10B experimental end-station, key features are highlighted.

Moving along the end-station, going from upstream-to-downstream (left to right in fig. 16), after VALVE-02 is a short transition pipe leading to a set of pivoting bellows. These allow for rotation of the test piece up to 2.7° and is used to set the incident angle of the dipole radiation as indicated in fig. 18. The end-station then consists of two similar pumping stations which are located either side of the test vessel. The pumping stations are equipped with cold-cathode gauges, residual gas analysers (RGA-03 and RGA-05), 300 l/s ion pumps and NEG cartridge pumps (1900 l/s for H₂). The downstream pumping station has an additional 240 l/s turbomolecular pump fitted for gas injection recovery and features a fixed photon absorber. The pressures in the end-station are at or below 1×10^{-10} mbar.

Also available on the end-station is a gas injection system consisting of four sample cylinders feeding through an electronically controlled leak valve. This can be used to inject gas at either end of the test vessel through the pumping systems.

Fig. 18: Schematic showing the “combined lateral offset and angular configuration” arrangement for irradiation of the FE10B test vessels.

Not highlighted in figs. 16 and 17 are the supporting instrumentation including pneumatics, thermocouples and water cooling as required for all beam-facing components.

A change of test vessel requires the end-station to be vented. However, as the end-station and its pumps can be isolated from the remainder of the front-end, this limits the vented volume to the pumping stations and test vessel only. A bake-out is still necessary to recover to UHV pressures and to activate NEG-coated test vessels.

3.1.3 Data collection and analysis

The total and partial pressures collected from the cold-cathode gauges and the residual gas analysers are stored in a remote data archiver. This allows for straightforward recall of the pressure data which can then be used for programmatic analysis. This has been achieved using MATLAB scripts which access the archiver and retrieve data from the relevant experimental time periods. The data is then interpolated to align the timescales and ensures that the RGA partial- and cold cathode total-pressures are consistent. The data can then be processed according to the method and type of vessel installed, and the required $\Delta P/I_{beam}$ or PSD yield datasets are calculated and plotted.

There are two methods for determining the PSD yields using FE10B. The first uses the conductance-limiting orifice to provide a known pumping speed, this requires no pumping on the end-station. The pressure difference across the orifice is measured using RGAs and this can be used to determine the gas flow through the orifice, before being converted to PSD yield.

The second method is the ‘three-gauge method’ as described by Malyshev et al [5,21]. This requires the addition of a third RGA to the end-station, which is located at the centre of the test vessel (RGA-04 in fig. 17). The difference in measured pressure between this central gauge (RGA-04) and the average of the pumping station pressures (RGA-03 and RGA-05) can then be attributed to gas desorbed by incident radiation. In the case of a non-pumping surface this can straightforwardly be used to determine the PSD yield. However, in the case of a pumping surface then the measured gas excess is a combination of the desorbed gas due to incident radiation and the re-pumped gas due to the activated, pumping, surface. If the sticking probability is well-known, or can be determined in-situ, then the contribution removed by the pumping surface can be calculated and the PSD yields determined. In this case, pumping is required on the end-station as the gas density distribution only inside the vessel is considered.

3.1.4 Preliminary results and conclusions

Shown below in fig. 19 are preliminary $\Delta P/I$ plots for hydrogen (H_2), methane (CH_4), carbon monoxide (CO) and carbon dioxide (CO_2). These plots compare the three vessels measured on FE10B to date: uncoated (baked) and NEG-coated (unbaked) stainless-steel vessels, along with the coated (baked) OFS-Cu vessel.

Fig. 19: $\Delta P/I$ plots obtained for a) H_2 , b) CH_4 , c) CO and d) CO_2 .

Each sub-plot includes data from the uncoated (baked) (red) and NEG-coated (unbaked) (blue) stainless-steel vessels as well as the coated (baked) OFS-Cu vessel (black).

Comparing the uncoated (baked) and NEG-coated (unbaked) stainless-steel vessels. For H_2 , see fig. 19 (a), the dynamic pressures are similar between the two vessel types, indicating that the NEG layer can act as a hydrogen diffusion barrier. This changes for methane, **Error! Reference source not found.**(b), where the NEG-coating dynamic pressure is a factor of five higher. Note that the CH_4 pressures have been derived from mass 15 (CH_3) to avoid the influence of atomic oxygen from either O_2 or H_2O .

In fig. 19 (c) and (d), showing CO and CO_2 , the dynamic pressures are initially higher for the NEG-coated vessel by up to a factor of 10 and 25, respectively. However, they become comparable at higher photon doses. It is worth noting that higher mass gas molecules will have more of an effect on the stored beam, and that the higher dynamic pressures observed for the NEG-coating (unbaked) will more strongly impact machine vacuum performance.

For all four of the gases investigated, the dynamic pressure is higher for the NEG-coated (unbaked) vessel implying that the PSD yields are also higher. Although, for H₂ and CH₄, the two materials have relatively similar desorption behaviour, but this is not the case for CO and CO₂.

Furthermore, baking provides a modest reduction in desorption for the uncoated vessel which is not seen for the unbaked NEG-coated vessel.

Following the data presented above, two activation cycles were performed on the NEG-coated stainless-steel vessel. The first was to 180 °C for 24 hours while the second was to 190 °C for a further 24 hours. After each activation cycle, the vessel was irradiated for a period of between 6 and 8 weeks. This data is shown in fig. 20 and expands the photon dose scale from fig. 19 to values above 1×10²³ photons/m. Following the two activation cycles and subsequent irradiation periods, the end-station was then vented to 1 atm. of high-purity N₂ (Air Product BIP N₂, 6.0N) for 30 minutes. After recovery back to UHV conditions, the test vessel was irradiated again.

Fig. 20: $\Delta P/I$ curves comparing the stainless-steel vessels at high photon dose. Note that the coated vessel has been at a dose of around 5×10^{23} photons/m and subsequently vented to high-purity N₂. Shown are curves for the following gases: a) H₂, b) CH₄, c) CO and d) CO₂.

From fig. 20, the dynamic pressures for H₂ and CO show only a small reduction while there is no clear change for CH₄ or CO₂. However, the effect of baking on these pressure values may only be small owing to the high photon doses and cumulative cleaning effect.

It should be noted that the molecular masses for CO and N₂ are nearly identical at 28 amu (this is within typical RGA mass resolution range). The analysis used for fig. 20 (c) assumes CO is the main source of gas at this mass. It would be expected that the venting process would provide a source of additional N₂ adsorbed on the vessel walls. As such, an increase in the CO signal might be expected after beginning irradiation and this is observed, with the dynamic pressure consistent with pre-vented levels. With the current analysis it is not possible to quantify the contributions to the dynamic pressure from CO and N₂ separately.

Overall, for all four gases, a small change in dynamic pressure is seen and this suggests that the NEG coating has not been activated. However, the reduction in dynamic pressure for H₂ and CO indicates that baking a NEG-coated vessel, even if not successfully activated, can reduce the photon-induced outgassing.

This is further supported when comparing the NEG-coated (baked) OFS-Cu vessel with the NEG-coated (unbaked) stainless-steel vessel, as shown in fig. 19. Here the dynamic pressures are all broadly consistent, with the OFS-Cu vessel having a lower dynamic pressure than the unbaked NEG-coated stainless-steel vessel. However, the effect of the reduced vessel bore of the OFS-Cu vessel (20 mm compared to 35 mm) on the vacuum conductance will result in a decrease in the PSD yields. The net effect should be to have a lower overall PSD yield in comparison to the uncoated stainless-steel or NEG-coating without baking.

The behaviour of the uncoated and NEG-coated vessels installed on FE10B has been consistent with that reported in the literature and at partner institutions. The data presented here has focussed primarily on non-pumping surfaces, either non-coated vessel walls or non-activated NEG surfaces. The typically observed conditioning behaviour of vessels exposed to high photon doses is observed and we see that the difference in dynamic pressure reduces as we reach doses upwards of 1×10^{23} photons/m or 400 A·h of Diamond operational time.

The three-gauge method has been successfully used to determine the dynamic pressure behaviour of these vessels and their coatings. With careful consideration of the RGA behaviour and calibrations of the gauges on the FE10B end-station, determination of the PSD yields is possible. The ability to compare the three distinct vessel types (based on two test vessel designs) will allow for transferable results that can be compared with other facilities and used in the design of new facilities.

Based on these results, it may be possible to consider a limited machine start-up in the case of unbaked or non-activated NEG-coated vessels. However, the gas load may be disproportionately high during the initial commissioning phase, and this will place unwanted burden on other pumping elements within the system. However, the long-term effects of synchrotron radiation result in vessels with similar vacuum performance despite their initial differences in desorption. Equally, baking a NEG-coated vessel, even in the case of unsuccessful activation, provides a benefit through the reduction of the total photon-induced outgassing.

The next steps, working within the framework of the I.FAST project Task 10.5, will be to focus on activation of the OFS-Cu vessel and comparison with the data collected at SOLEIL.

3.2 TEST AT SYNCHROTRON SOLEIL

3.2.1 Introduction

From 2013 to 2017, a small front-end was equipped at SOLEIL to irradiate vacuum chambers with photons from dipole D08 (see fig. 21). A small in-tunnel beamline called at this time D08-1 FLUOX, had been built in order to study fluorescence from synchrotron radiation through aluminium NEG coated vacuum chambers. From 2019 to 2020, the Vacuum Group had the opportunity to modify this beam-exit for photodesorption studies in the framework of the SOLEIL upgrade project, benefiting from synchrotron radiation of SOLEIL (see fig. 22). The initial simple front-end was added a mobile diaphragm for photon beam shaping, and high capacity UHV pumping with a small conductance for desorption measurements (see fig. 23), allowing the study of outgassed molecules desorbed by impinging photons on an irradiated vacuum chamber which is of great interest for particle accelerators [22,23]. The goal was to characterize photodesorption yield in NEG-coated vacuum chamber of decreasing diameters, to go forward with small apertures and small conductances vacuum chambers required for future SOLEIL machine upgrade. At this time, was also elaborated the IFAST Task 10.5 Task proposal for PSD studies on NEG coatings for accelerators. A dedicated experimental setup was foreseen to be installed on the SOLEIL’s PSD beamline for that purpose, equipped with special vacuum chambers dedicated to NEG characterization with 3-gauge method [5,21].

Fig. 21: Synchrotron Beam Shape from D08-1.

Fig. 22: Early Version of D08-1 PSD Front-End.

Fig. 23: Irradiation Principal Diagram of PSD Front-End.

3.2.2 PSD beamline D08-1

The actual PSD Front-End (see fig. 24) is composed, from upstream to downstream, of a photon shutter (OCC.1), a vacuum gate valve (VS.1), a first sputter ion pump of 150 l/s (PI.1) in front of the motorized diaphragm assembly, and separated by a second vacuum gate valve (VS.2) from the high speed pumping station with two sputter ion pumps of 500 l/s each (PI.2 & PI.3), then comes the conductance aperture (V 6 mm x H 40 mm, 28.3 l/s for N₂) and just after, the first measuring/pumping assembly with a turbo molecular pump of 100 l/s (PTUR.2). Here can be used, upstream the experimental setup, extraction gauges (JBA.1 & JBA.2), a cold cathode gauge (JPEN.3) and a residual gas analyser (RGA.2 not shown).

Fig.24: Actual D08-1 PSD Front-End at SOLEIL.

The experimental test vacuum vessel is here represented by a simple tube, but can be equipped in the middle by a cold cathode gauge (JPEN.1) and a second residual gas analyser. The terminal end is equipped with a second photon shutter (OCC.2) and is back pumped by another 100 l/s turbo molecular pump (PTUR.1), and also equipped for vacuum measurements, with an extraction gauge (JBA.3), a cold cathode gauge (JPEN.4) and a residual gas analyser (RGA.1). Turbo-molecular

pumps can be isolated for the experiment with vacuum gate valves (VS.5 and VS.4). Everything is represented on fig. 24 with others measuring equipment as thermocouples (TC.x) for monitoring temperatures, primary gauges for vacuum security (JPIR.x), and flowmeters (DEB.x) for securing water-cooled parts. The measured vessel can be isolated by a vacuum valve (VS.3) and conveniently replaced, though it requires UHV baking-out or NEG activation.

3.2.3 Data collection and analysis

3.2.3.1 PSD measurement method

The experimental setup, or test vacuum vessel, can be characterized by measuring the pressure upstream (P1) and downstream (P3), thus measuring outgassing or photodesorption when irradiated with photons (the so-called Photon Stimulated Desorption). By adding a pressure measurement in the middle (P2), it is possible to characterize the behaviour of the tested chamber even if the chamber present pumping properties induced by NEG-coatings when activated. It may be possible to know the whole pressure profile along its length. There, can be applied the 3-gauge method ^{Error! Bookmark not defined.} that allows, in principle, to calculate both PSD yield and sticking coefficient, by measuring pressures at upstream, in the middle and at downstream in two different pressures conditions. The variation of pressure required can be applied by injecting a gas species during irradiation or varying pumping speed. The last method was chosen as already implemented on the front-end by opening or closing the gate in front of the downstream turbomolecular pump. When there is no other pumping than the NEG test chamber (turbomolecular pumps isolated, gates closed), the pressure measurement in front of the experimental setup allows to estimate the gas flux and the photodesorption yield with the standard flux method. That was done for many years at SOLEIL and the 3-gauge method could be developed by adding a central measuring port on tested vacuum chambers. Then “3-gauges” PSD samples vacuum chambers were developed for the IFAST collaboration in which could be studied NEG pumping and PSD properties on the existing front-end at SOLEIL.

3.2.3.2 Schedule of PSD measurements

From 2022 to 2023, all necessary parts for the IFAST experiment were designed, tested in vacuum lab before installation inside the SOLEILS's tunnel. The schedule of the IFAST tests had to accommodate with other experiments planned on the PSD Front-End, and all experiments were subject to the availability of the tunnel access between SOLEIL user operation runs. The access is only possible for long periods during machine shutdowns, generally for a few weeks, and on machine-dedicated time that takes places on Mondays only. For this reason, complex scheduling had to be done with typically: the installation of the test chamber during a machine shutdown, followed by a first experimental run with NEG-coating non-activated. We then need to benefit from a first Monday to prepare NEG activation before proceeding during one week of operation and requires another next Monday to prepare the experiment for beam irradiation. The next experiment with NEG-activated also had to be initiated on a machine dedicated time on a Monday, and then data could be acquired during the rest of the user's operations. So, a complete experiment would require at least three weeks after a machine shutdown, before gathering data until the next shutdown. Nevertheless, it was finally possible to have the PSD setup running in IFAST configuration in April 2023. The actual IFAST experiment would have to wait for the availability of an NEG-coated PSD sample deposited in UKRI lab. The first PSD sample, referred as IFAST#1, was received at SOLEIL and tested "ready for

installation" beginning 2024. Following the exposed principle, it was installed on PSD F-E in April 2024 (see figs. 25 and 26). The first experiment with a dense NEG-coating of 1 μm from UKRI not activated was done on the Monday 27th of April, followed by the NEG activation first week of June 2024, and a second experiment with NEG activated on the Monday 10th of June. IFAST#1 PSD sample had been irradiated and data collected since then and until the end of SOLEIL users' operation run 3, till end-July 2024.

Fig. 25: PSD Front-End equipped with IFAST#1 PSD Sample in April 2024.

Fig. 26: IFAST#1 PSD sample experimental setup installed on PSD Front-End.

3.2.4 Preliminary Results and Conclusions

Despite the fact that the experimental setup was equipped with RGA, only total pressure measurements could be exploited at this time. The pressure measured in front of the tested chamber should allow to calculate the PSD yield by the flux method, and measuring the three pressures in front, in the middle and at the back of the chamber should allow to apply the 3-gauge method. Nevertheless, the first most significant measurement is to represent the increase of pressure in the

middle of the chamber normalized to the current of the machine versus the accumulated photon beam dose (see fig. 28).

Fig. 27: Pressure Increase normalized to the Machine Current Versus Accumulated Photon Dose

Fig. 28: Photo Stimulated Desorption Yield Versus Accumulated Photon Dose.

The evolution of the pressures that follows the reduction of the PSD yield clearly shows a typical behaviour of commissioning with beam scrubbing effect expected for vacuum chambers exposed to synchrotron radiation. The activation of the NEG coating at low photon dose improves the decrease of the PSD yield by an order of magnitude. This effect, that could even be more important depending on the NEG-coating properties, is of great interest for early future machine commissioning. The activation of NEG-coating could be required for low conductance next generation synchrotron, benefiting from the significant reduction of the PSD yield, more than the in situ pumping speed that it brings, and could be compulsory for starting next generation machines within a reasonable time frame.

Fig. 29: 3-Gauge Experimental Parameters and Sticking Coefficient Versus Accumulated Photon Dose.

At this time, exploitation of the data is still ongoing and needs to be analysed, but a first attempt of calculations was done with the 3-gauge method on total pressures making extreme assumptions on gas composition, which allow to display high and low boundaries for PSD yield (see fig. 28). Corresponding sticking coefficients calculated from 3-gauge experiment parameter is also displayed versus accumulated photon dose (see fig. 29). These results have been discussed during latest 5th IFAST meeting of Task 10.5 on the 24th of April 2024.

4 Future plans / Conclusion / relation to other IFAST work

This report is describing the progress in the Task 10.5 from initial idea to measure PSD from NEG coated samples on SR beamline to first results obtained on two SR beamlines at DLS and SOLEIL. The collaboration includes 4 partners: DESY, DLS, SOLEIL and STFC/UKRI. Working jointly the team has designed the standard samples for the collaboration, has agreed on measurement procedure and data analysis, an intense knowledge and sample exchange is taking place.

After completing measurements on SR beamlines, the sample will be sent to STFC/UKRI for further characterising the NEG films with SEM and other surface characterisation techniques. Other samples for testing at SR beamlines at DLS and SOLEIL are under preparation. The joint collaboration work will continue for the entire duration of IFAST and beyond.

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Annex: Glossary

Acronym	Definition
NEG	Non-evaporable getter
PSD	Photon stimulated desorption
RGA	Residual Gas Analyser